

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *In preschool education, a child is prepared for a comprehensive school. Among them, the development of children's speech is one of the most important. It is important for them to be able to speak freely and fully express their thoughts.*

Keywords: *education, toys, fiction, preparation, early childhood education, storytelling*

The content of improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children is developed in harmony with the content of the educational activity of the preschool educational institution. In developing the content of improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children, they come from the general laws about the decisive importance of social life conditions and education in the formation of human personality.

One of these laws is that even if a child comes into the world with certain innate abilities, these abilities do not strictly determine his character and the level of development, but only create a certain natural ground for his spiritual development. Every mentally healthy child has hidden potential, the only problem is to create favorable conditions for their emergence and realization.

An important condition for full mental development is the timely and correct acquisition of speech by the child. The content of the mother tongue teaching program in the preschool educational institution is aimed at forming children's speech generalization, simple understanding of language and speech phenomena, interest in various aspects of speech activity, control of their own speech, which gives a creative character to the process of child speech development.

In order to form social adaptation, it is possible to develop interest in language richness, develop the ability to use various means of expression in one's own speech, and turn children's speech into an impressive, sincere and lively speech. In this direction, creating circles in preschool educational institutions, their goal is to activate word creativity, which is an important indicator of the development of children's speech.

Social adaptation is formed taking into account the level of development of the society, taking into account the positive experience of various pedagogic systems, as well as knowledge about the nature of the child.

Trainings on the formation of social adaptation in the preschool educational institution are organized on the basis of a complex approach. In order to provide it from a methodological point of view, a unique development technology was developed, which is directed to the development of different, but interconnected, adaptations within one training session.

In the construction of this system, the interrelationship of various tasks that come at each age level in its own way served as a guiding principle. This is the reason why it is necessary to be careful in solving tasks related to social adaptation.

The main goal of social adaptation in pre-school educational institutions is the creative assimilation of the norms and rules of social activity, the ability to use them in specific situations, and the acquisition of basic communication skills. According to scientist A.V.Zaporozhye opinion, even without special education, children show great interest in the reality of language from a very young age, observe both the spiritual and grammatical aspects of language, and create new words. Only a small number of them reach a high level in natural speech development, so it is necessary to teach speech and speech communication in a targeted way [1].

It is particularly important to analyze the society's focus on supporting pre-school education, students' appeal to their help to prepare children for social adaptation, and rational organization of their social and personal life. In order to understand these forms, children are guilty, and destinations that are determined to do, and target the values, and the assimilation of themselves, understand, and self-fulfillment, understanding, and selfishí Al. hash .

Mental, spiritual and aesthetic education of children in the preschool educational institution is carried out in the process of social adaptation. It is known that the content of social adaptation mastered by a child of high school age is the adaptation reflected in his mind and accepted by his sense organs. The content of social adaptation of a preschooler includes aesthetic concepts related to the concept of duty to the surrounding people and nature, and ideas about social life events and holidays. Therefore, the work of shaping social adaptation determines the work of introducing children to the environment, as well as artistic literature, and determines the forms of these work.

Speech education is closely connected with the formation of artistic and speech activity, that is, with aesthetic education. In preschool educational institutions, children are introduced to folklore and literary works, so preschoolers learn to use the means of expression of their mother tongue.

Acquaintance with literature, narrating works of art, teaching to create a story as a team helps not only social adaptation, but also the formation of moral behavior of preschool children.

The system of social adaptation helps to master the structural elements of the language in a thorough approach. In this case, the creation of the most favorable pedagogical conditions for the development of language abilities of preschool children is the main factor.

The task of forming such generalizations is important in the formation of the grammatical structure of the speech.

In this case, the development of speech is evaluated not only in the field of linguistics (in the form of the child's acquisition of phonetic, lexical, grammatical language skills), but also in the field of communication with each other and adults (in the form of communicative skills), which also includes speech culture, It is also important for the formation of social adaptation.

Since social adaptation is a long series of conditional reflexes, pedagogues try to observe as much as possible the constant connection between the influence (teaching) of an adult on children and their reactions. This approach lays the foundation for the child's social adaptation at the preschool level.

In order to improve the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children, it ensures a wide awareness of children's language phenomena in connection with other sections of work on speech. For example, the formation of students' sound and syllabic structure of the word, familiarization with the word content of the sentence, the analysis of the sounds of the word, at the same time, about the formation of words and semantic relations, about the content structure of fluent speech. prepares imaginations for development.

Many years of research show that in the formation of social adaptation in children, they need auxiliary tools that facilitate and direct the process of its formation. According to S.L.Rubinshteyn[2], one of such factors is the demonstrative nature of the speech act. The second auxiliary tool is the modeling of the speech plan.

Researchers say that children of preschool age have social adaptation, but they point out that this is not educationally oriented. Therefore, while analyzing children's speech, the pedagogue pays attention not only to poorly structured sentences, but also to the existence of sentences related to purpose, reason and time.

A child whose social adaptation is not sufficiently formed is treated differently. Some parents believe that in time the child will catch up with his peers. Lagging behind in social adaptation leaves a serious mark on the child's overall growth, prevents him from fully communicating and playing with his peers, makes it difficult to perceive the environment, aggravates the child's emotional and mental condition.

The higher the mobility of the child, the better his speech is developed. The relationship between general and speech mobility A.A. Leontev[3], A.R.Luria[4]. It has been studied and confirmed in the researches of many great scientists such When the child acquires movement abilities and skills, coordination of movements develops. The formation of actions occurs with the participation of speech.

In order to improve the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children, the pedagogue listens and remembers the tasks of preschool children, for example, the development of motor skills in children, offering the child exercises suitable for his age and capabilities, simple exercises aimed at the development of general motor skills, and then improve preparation for teaching performance.

Researchers have worked out the principles, content and methods of mental education of children, and it will give them the opportunity to significantly increase the developmental results of social adaptation education, its impact on the development of mental abilities.

Social adaptation is a means of intellectual development. At the same time, the educator develops the child's mind during social adjustment. Intellectual development is the central task of a pedagogue in a preschool educational institution.

The power of social adaptation as a mental development factor and an educational factor of emotions and will exists in its nature, i.e. in the feature of serving as a means of communication between a person and the environment.

In improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children, the importance of the readiness to implement the following was determined, while recalling the importance of children's speech development.

Speech development in children as a factor of social adaptation

The content of the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children includes a system of works on the development of speech. It consists of the close relationship between these components and complementing each other.

1. The educator has to work hard on creating a developmental environment.
2. Conversations, games and playful exercises aimed at enriching and activating the child's speech.

The student should always be prepared for the fact that the child does not understand the speech addressed to him, and sometimes even the words or grammatical forms he pronounces. There are various forms of manifestation of such incomprehensibility.

It is possible that the child does not combine the sounds he has heard and liked, or simply repeats the words, even if he pronounces the words correctly, he does not give them any meaning.

It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the majority of children cannot learn the meanings of high-level generalization words when improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children; they usually understand these words very narrowly. Sometimes the narrowing of the understanding on the part of the child is so unexpected that it is difficult for the teacher to quickly understand the reason for the mistake. Children often use words with partial understanding, and sometimes without understanding them at all, that is why they often use them inappropriately, without knowing the true meaning of the words and phrases they are using. This idea related to children's speech is especially valuable compared to the words used by children, which express their ideas about time and space, the way of actions. Accordingly, it is necessary to pay special attention to these in improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children.

When preparing to introduce a word into the child's personal dictionary, the student must prevent its misunderstanding or misunderstanding: for this, he has a methodical way of explaining words of various degrees of generalization, figurative words. It is necessary to know them and be able to use these methods skillfully. Sometimes a child does not understand the speech of an older person due to the use of general expressions that are not fully spoken, typical of conversational speech.

In children, social adaptation appears before other mental processes and is involved in all types of activity. It influences the speech and mental development of the child, and shapes the personality in general. Social adaptation is manifested in dialogue. Dialogue occurs in more free speech communication and serves as a basis for children's pronunciation, natural development of grammatical skills, enrichment of vocabulary, acquisition of fluent speech skills. Dialog is also taught in special classes, but such classes usually take place once or twice a month; and in free communication, the child engages in dialogue with the teacher and other children during the whole time in the kindergarten. New words and phrases are learned in social adaptation. It helps to implement the activity of social adaptation in the order of simple algorithmic action, on the basis of premeditation, it helps to accelerate the pace of development of mental processes (Y.O.Smirnova[5]). Implementation of social adaptation is carried out more in the form of a conversation, that is, an exchange of ideas between adults and children or children themselves. In the process of social adaptation, the ability to hold a conversation, that is, the ability to conduct a dialogue, is developed, and, therefore, speech is enriched with appropriate syntactic forms and a vocabulary reflecting this area of reality. The speech of preschoolers is accepted as a positive event that happens to someone in the process of conversation.

In the pre-school educational institution, the conversation was held directly for the purpose of developing children's speech. But the speech definitely reflects the real events, so the conversation in the preschool educational institution also gives knowledge. The content of the interviews is determined by the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children and the children's upbringing and education program.

The formation of social adaptation in time depends on the general speech culture, that is, the child's normal speech communication with peers and adults, good mastery of literacy, mastering school programs after going to school. .

The aspect of social adaptation related to speech is mainly formed in preschool age. In classes and daily communication, the teacher trains children to pronounce words clearly, to use the intonation tools of expressions correctly, to teach them to speak loudly enough, without haste, and to develop the ability to hear sounds and speech. All of these are of great importance for the development of children's speech communication: the purposefulness of the voice reaction, the focus on another person, the ability to hear speech, and the voluntary formation of pronunciation are formed (S.L.Rubinstein [6]).

R.Ye.Levina writes: "When choosing ways and means to eliminate and prevent speech disorders in children, it is necessary to aim at the most important results, which are related to the normal development of speech processes." Therefore, the most important part in the system of correcting the general slow development of speech of a preschool age child is the reception of sounds and the analysis of sounds. So, the child's speech develops in harmony with the formation of his thinking [7].

When forming social adaptation, it should not be forgotten that the child spends a lot of time outside the kindergarten: with his family, peers, etc. His vocabulary is rich in communication with the people around him. The child learns to express his opinion on this or that issue, to pronounce sounds correctly, to form phrases. If the child is engaged in speech not only in the preschool educational institution, but also in the family, he will master the speech more effectively. Parents have a good understanding of the tasks of upbringing and education, know some methodological methods used by educators in working on the development of children's speech, they will undoubtedly help in organizing speech classes at home. Promotion of knowledge among parents about the issues of children's speech development is carried out by the pedagogue, first of all, during conversations and consultations. Other forms of work are also effective: visual promotion, for example, organizing stands with information about the level of formation of sound pronunciation in each child, hanging tables showing the correct accents in difficult words for children. to eat publish small notes and articles on the development of speech in children of preschool age in the parents' corner; delivering lectures with the involvement of specialists [8].

When preparing to work with parents, what and how students should do with the child at home, it is practical for the preschool child to feel interest in speech training, not only to learn, to form certain skills and abilities. acquires the knowledge to give instructions on how to use the material.

The improvement of the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children was shown in the ability to work with parents. Taking into account that the correct pronunciation of sounds and the acquisition of other aspects of the spoken speech do not happen equally in all children, parents do not lag behind in the speech development of their children, when to pronounce this or that sound correctly. Many are interested in research. In the process of learning the correct pronunciation of sounds, students should be prepared to conduct conversations about when and what sounds appear in children, what defects in speech are related to the child's young characteristics.

In the course of speech, R.Ye.Levina [7], G.A.Nikashina[8] divides the leading place into the perception of sounds, that is, the formation of the ability to receive and distinguish speech sounds (phonemes).

In improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children, attention is paid to the following:

- do not burden the child with complex speech material;
- do not force the child to repeat incomprehensible words
- do not memorize poems that are complex in terms of form, content and volume;
- not teaching him to pronounce sounds that are difficult for him due to the lack of readiness of the articulation organs;
- forcing to read fiction intended for school-aged children.

It is necessary to always remember that the child's learning to speak is inextricably linked with his mental and spiritual development in the conversation with the parents. By expanding the scope of the child's imagination about the objects and events around him, introducing him to literary works, talking with the child about various household topics that are close and understandable to him, parents not only expand his worldview, but also help him quickly acquire correct speech. The student needs to learn how to help.

Summarizing the advanced experience of raising a child in the family and conveying it to the parents at the meetings, as an important task of the pedagogue, the skills to perform these tasks are formed in the students.

In improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children, the student is the first, first and foremost, to support the word in the order of greatest importance. , it is necessary to care about helping to create and strengthen imaginations and the creative ability to combine them.

In the process of social adaptation, children's worldview expands, thinking processes improve, new knowledge and abilities appear, and, therefore, speech also improves. However, children acquire thinking and speaking skills only through communication with others. As the child grows, the content of the communication becomes more complex, which, in turn, leads to the complexity of the forms of speech that it occurs.

The formation of social adaptation in children leads to the emergence of new relationships and new types of activity with adults, the leveling of speech functions and forms. There are new tasks of social adaptation, which consist of conveying the impressions collected by the child to an older person when he was not in direct contact with him. In social adaptation, communication skills such as a monologue-story about what you have experienced and seen appear.

It is necessary to emphasize that mastering the connected forms of speech is a complex and long-lasting process that requires skillful pedagogical influence and leadership. The development of fluent speech in a preschool-aged child is carried out in the daily life process and during training [8].

In the course of social adaptation, the student sets the following tasks for the future activity: to fluently tell a story about what children have seen and heard, to correctly reflect what is accepted in the speech, to speak coherently, with enough completeness and completeness, not to deviate from the topic teaching to tell a story slowly, teaching educators to tell a story without haste; to help them find the necessary words and phrases, to encourage the precise use of the names of objects, actions, properties; development of expressive speech, teaching to speak lively and impressive.

The formation of social adaptation in children involves giving children the right to choose activities in accordance with their interests, inclinations, and desires. The student should be able to create a developmental environment for the successful development of the child's speech and his activity.

The preparation of students to observe children and analyze the results of speech development, first of all, is a content based on an individual approach to each child. As a true diagnostician, the student is taught to evaluate the child not only on the basis of comparison with others, but also on the basis of comparison with himself.

Thus, improving the professional preparation of students for the formation of social adaptation in children implies the goal-oriented activity of students, a creative approach to its organization, and person-oriented models of influence, which succeeds in the formation of social adaptation in children.

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